

Paper 7

**AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON FACTORS INFLUENCING EDUCATIONAL
QUALITY THROUGH MOOC WITH REFERENCE TO MANGALURU**

Ms. Shaila Kamath

Assistant Professor, Besant Women’s College, Mangalore

Email: shazkamath68@gmail.com

&

Ms. Anupa Baliga B.S

Assistant Professor, Besant Women’s College, Mangalore

Email: anupabhandary@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Technology is a powerful tool that can support and transform education enabling new ways for people to learn and work together. Virtual learning through Massive Open Online Course is gaining more importance among faculty members and students in higher education in this era of technology. MOOC have introduced the skills and techniques of learning enabling the learners to gain a foothold in the competitive world. It presents to the learners how teaching and learning can be comprehended and executed in a better way. This paper explores the factors that enhance the quality in education through MOOC and examines the learning experiences of the learners. It further examines the effectiveness of virtual learning. The information for this study has been collected through convenience sampling method. Secondary data has been obtained by referring e-journals and other literatures. The global COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted all aspects of human activities and has caused a huge impact on education sector. It has resulted in increasing demand for virtual learning platforms and various online courses. A blended learning approach of classroom learning and virtual learning will have a significant impact in enhancing the quality of Higher Education.

Keywords: Technology, MOOC, Covid-19 Pandemic, Blended Learning, Higher Education.

Introduction:

Education is an indispensable tool to change the world and thus enhancing its quality becomes crucial. It contributes to the advancement of human development. There has been a dramatic change in the field of education through the incorporation of digital technology. Introduction of Massive Open Online Course is one among the change in higher education which enables the

“Total Quality Management in Education”

learners to gain a foothold in the competitive world.

MOOC being a significant developing trend in education has introduced major learning platforms like Swayam, Coursera, Futurelearn, Udacity, EDX offering courses covering all the fields including business, mathematics, computer science, social sciences, humanities, medicine, biology. The main purpose of virtual learning is to provide its learners to access the learning information at their own pace and at lower educational cost. The global COVID-19 pandemic has caused a direct impact on education sector. There has been a paradigm shift in the teaching and learning process globally. The face-to-face traditional classroom and virtual learning are to be optimally integrated such that the strengths of each are blended into a unique learning experience. The new normal has enabled to reinvent ways of learning and adopting strategies to maximize the learning outcomes and enhance quality in education.

Review of Literature:

Dr. Mohd. Faisal Khan and Dr. Fakhra Naeem (2021) have analysed the various impacts of Covid-19 on higher education in India which has created an opportunity for transition in Indian pedagogical approaches and intervention of virtual learning in all levels of education. Virtual learning has become the preferred means of education during this pandemic.

According to Noura Alhazzani (2020), MOOCs improves education outcomes thereby having a direct impact on higher education. A 65% improvement in higher education outcomes was accounted for by MOOCs and hence has a positive influence in higher education system. It has a direct impact on developing students learning and communication skills.

Nour Albelbisi, Farrah Dina Yusop, Umi Kalsum Mohd Salleh (2018) reveals main factors classified into three levels that is presage, process and product variables according to Biggs 3P model. These elements will ensure that the MOOC is designed and delivered effectively. It also ensures learning occurs meaningfully and results in satisfaction among MOOC learners.

Laxmisha Rai and Deng Chunrao (2016) reviews the reasons for success and failures of learners of MOOC. Some of the learners are genuinely interested in finishing the course, some learners are fascinated by the reputation of universities and quality of courses. The role of MOOC in reaching millions of learners around the world cannot be overlooked inspite of problems such as poor internet connectivity, lack of knowledge about MOOC, language barrier and level of learning potential.

“Total Quality Management in Education”

Need for the Study:

Digital revolution has the potential to transform education. MOOCs enhances the quality of education by incorporating blended learning. It is of significance to explore the factors that influences educational quality through MOOCs. It enables to achieve specific learning goals.

Objectives of the study:

1. To explore the factors that enhance the quality in education through MOOC
2. To examine the learning experiences of the respondents
3. To ascertain the demotivating factors of the respondents in the virtual learning

Research Design:

The primary data for this empirical study has been collected through an online survey using a structured questionnaire through google form. The data is collected from a sample of 50 respondents of Mangaluru city through convenience sampling method. Descriptive statistical percentage tool is being used to analyze the data to arrive at findings and conclusion. Secondary data has been obtained by referring e-journals and other literatures.

Limitations of the study:

- The sample size may not be very large enough to generalize the result.
- Another limitation of the study is time constraint
- The study is limited to the respondents of Mangaluru city

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Table showing the gender of the respondents being involved in the study

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	20	40
Female	30	60
Total	50	100

“Total Quality Management in Education”

Chart 1: Chart showing the gender of the respondents being involved in the study.

Interpretation: In the above chart it is seen that 40% of the males are involved in the study and 60% of the females are being interacted for the study.

Table 2: Table showing the age group of the respondents.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Below 30	10	20
30-39	30	60
40-49	05	10
Above 50	05	10
Total	50	100

“Total Quality Management in Education”

Chart 2: Chart showing the age group of the respondents.

Interpretation: From the above chart it is seen that 20% respondents are below 30 years, 60% of the respondents are in the age group 30-39, 10% each of the respondents are in the age group 40-49 and above 50 years respectively.

Table 3: Table showing the Educational Qualification of the respondents.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Graduate	20	40
Post graduate	25	50
Additional Qualification	05	10
Total	50	100

Interpretation: It is seen in the above chart that 40% of the respondents are Graduate, 50% of the respondents are Post Graduate and 10% of the respondents are holding additional Qualification like PhD and MPhil.

Table 4: Table showing the designation of the respondents

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Student	10	20
Lecturer	20	40
Research Scholar	15	30
Other	05	10
Total	50	100

“Total Quality Management in Education”

Chart 4: Chart showing the designation of the respondents.

Interpretation: From the above chart it is clear that 20% of the respondent belong to student category, 40% are lecturers, 30% are research scholars and 10% are professionals.

Table 5: Table showing the number of online courses taken up by the respondents

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	35	70
2	10	20
3	03	06
4 or more	02	04
Total	50	100

“Total Quality Management in Education”

Chart 5: Chart showing the number of online courses taken up by the respondents.

Interpretation: From the above chart it is clear that 70% of the respondents have taken up 1 online course, 20% of the respondents have taken up 2 online courses, 6% of the respondents have taken up 3 courses and 4% of the respondents have taken up 4 or more online courses.

Table 6: Table showing the Global Platforms that have been registered by respondents for taking up online courses.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Swayam	28	56
FutureLearn	12	24
Coursera	5	10
EdX	3	06
Others	2	04
Total	50	100

Chart 6: Chart showing the Global Platforms that have been registered by respondents for taking up online courses.

Interpretation: From the above chart it is clear that 56% of the respondents have registered for Swayam, 24% of the respondents have registered for FutureLearn, 10% of the respondents have registered for Coursera, 6% of the respondents have registered for EdX and 4% of the respondents registered for other global platform like Udacity and Udemy.

“Total Quality Management in Education”

Table 7: Table showing the number of hours per week spent by the respondents on Digital platforms.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
< 1 Hour	05	10
1-5 Hours	25	50
5-10 Hours	12	24
>10 Hours	08	16
Total	50	100

Chart 7: Chart showing the number of hours per week spent by the respondents on Digital platforms.

Interpretation: From the above chart it is clear that 10% of the respondents spend less than 1 hour per week on digital platforms, 50% of the respondents spend 1-5 hours per week on digital platforms, 24% of the respondents spend 5-10 hours per week on digital platforms and 16% of the respondents spend more than 10 hours per week on digital platforms.

“Total Quality Management in Education”

Table 8: Table showing the factors that enhance the quality of higher education through virtual learning.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Learn variety of subjects	07	14
Abundant learning resources	11	22
Online interaction & Group Discussion	05	10
Research and Presentation	10	20
Develops teaching and learning skills	03	06
Personalised learning	01	02
Flexibility in learning	01	02
Accessibility at convenience	12	24
Other	00	00
Total	50	100

Chart 8: Chart showing the factors that enhance the quality of higher education through virtual learning.

Interpretation: In the above chart it is clear that 14% of the respondents are of the opinion that the quality of higher education enhances by learning variety of subjects, 22% of the respondents state that abundant learning resources enhances quality, 10% of the respondents state that online

“Total Quality Management in Education”

interaction and group discussion enhances quality, 20% state that quality is enhanced through research and presentation, 6% of the respondents state that quality enhances by developing teaching and learning skills, 24% of the respondents are of the opinion that quality increases because of accessibility at convenience and 2% each of the respondents state that quality enhances through Personalised learning and flexibility in learning.

Table 9: Table showing the demotivating factors that affect the learning process of the respondents.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Lack of face to face learning	15	30
Lack of self-motivation	20	40
Feel isolated in learning online	07	14
Difficult to study online	05	10
Other	03	06
Total	50	100

Chart 9: Chart showing the demotivating factors that affect the learning process of the respondents.

Interpretation: 30% of the respondents state that they are demotivated because of lack of face to face interaction, 40% state lack of self-motivation, 14% state that isolation is the demotivating problem, 5% are of the opinion that it is difficult to study online and 3% state that they find

“Total Quality Management in Education”

difficult to understand the high level of English used in the courses.

Table 10: Table showing the satisfaction level of respondents in enhancing knowledge through virtual learning- MOOC.

Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	18	36
Satisfied	15	30
Neutral	10	20
Dissatisfied	05	10
Highly Dissatisfied	02	04
Total	50	100

Chart 10: Chart showing the satisfaction level of respondents in enhancing knowledge through virtual learning- MOOC.

Interpretation: From the above chart it is clear that 36% of the respondents are highly satisfied in enhancing knowledge through virtual learning, 30% of the respondents are satisfied in enhancing knowledge through virtual learning, 20% of the respondents are neutral, 10% of the respondents are dissatisfied and 4% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied.

“Total Quality Management in Education”

Table 11: Table showing the extent to which virtual learning will contribute towards enhancing the quality in education.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
To a small extent	07	14
To some extent	05	10
To a moderate extent	10	20
To a great extent	15	30
To a very great extent	13	26
Total	50	100

Chart 11: Chart showing the extent to which virtual learning will contribute towards enhancing the quality in education.

Interpretation: From the above chart it is clear that 14% of the respondents state that virtual learning contributes towards enhancing the quality in education to a small extent, 10% state that it is contributing to some extent, 20% to a moderate extent, 30% of the respondents state that virtual learning contributes to a great extent and 26% of the respondents are of the opinion that virtual learning contributes to a very great extent.

Findings:

1. 40% of the males are involved in the study and 60% of the females are being interacted for the study.
2. 20% respondents are below 30 years, 60% of the respondents are in the age group 30-39, 10% each of the respondents are in the age group 40- 49 and above 50 years respectively.

“Total Quality Management in Education”

3. 40% of the respondents are Graduate, 50% of the respondents are Post Graduate and 10% of the respondents are holding additional Qualification like PhD and MPhil.
4. 20% of the respondents belong to student category, 40% are lecturers, 30% are research scholars and 10% are professionals.
5. 70% of the respondents have taken up 1 online course, 20% of the respondents have taken up 2 online courses, 6% of the respondents have taken up 3 courses and 4% of the respondents have taken up 4 or more online courses.
6. 56% of the respondents have registered for Swayam, 24% of the respondents have registered for Future Learn, 10% of the respondents have registered for Coursera, 6% of the respondents have registered for EdX and 4% of the respondents registered for other global platform like Udacity and Udemy.
7. 10% of the respondents spend less than 1hour per week on digital platforms, 50% of the respondents spend 1-5 hours per week on digital platforms, 24% of the respondents spend 5-10 hours per week on digital platforms and 16% of the respondents spend more than 10 hours per week on digital platforms.
8. 24% of the respondents are of the opinion that quality increases because of accessibility at convenience.
9. 30% of the respondents state that they are demotivated because of lack of face to face interaction, 40% state lack of self-motivation, 14% state that isolation is the demotivating problem, 5% are of the opinion that it is difficult to study online and 3% state that they find difficult to understand the high level of English used in the courses.
10. 36% of the respondents are highly satisfied in enhancing knowledge through virtual learning.
11. 30% of the respondents state that virtual learning contributes to a great extent.

Suggestions:

- The course completion rates of learners can be improved through motivation and interactive content enabling the learners to overcome the obstacles.
- Use of some tools based on ICT can help in attending the needs of the learners at the right time.
- For an active and collaborative learning teaching methodologies for virtual learning can be developed.
- They can also provide a reflexive and motivational learning experience by designing innovative and creative educational materials to the learners.

“Total Quality Management in Education”

- Even learners need to be educated with the skills needed to use ICT to promote creative and critical thinking.
- Language used and the content included in the online courses should be made more simple.

Conclusion:

In today's world of technology there is a need to change the teaching and learning pedagogy. The education pattern has been transformed seeking a blended learning of traditional classroom and virtual learning to be included in the teaching pedagogy. MOOC integrate social networking, accessible online resources, and are facilitated by leading practitioners in the field of study. MOOC build on the engagement of learners who self-organize their participation according to learning goals, prior knowledge and skills, and common interests. Online education has given an opportunity to take up additional **courses** along with the studies or job as per the convenience of the people. But each and every aspect in life will have both pros and cons which should be tried to overcome in the near future.

References:

- Alhazzani, N. (2020). MOOC's impact on higher education. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 2(1), 1-6.
- Albelbisi, N., Yusop, F. D., & Salleh, U. K. M. (2018). Mapping the factors influencing success of massive open online courses (MOOC) in higher education. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 14(7), 2995-3012.
- Rai, L., & Chunrao, D. (2016). Influencing factors of success and failure in MOOC and general analysis of learner behavior. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(4), 262-268.
- Khan, M. F., & Naeem, F. (2021). Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Higher Education in India. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research*, 8(4), 1-9.
